

CREATION OF NEW ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE TEXTILE MATERIALS

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The presence of pilot production of metallized electrically conductive fiber nitron (EPVN) in our Republic led to the establishment of research in the field of creating special textile materials with specified electrophysical characteristics to solve urgent problems associated with static electricity, electrical high voltage and electromagnetic radiation.

Scientific research is carried out in the following areas:

- creation of antistatic (non-electrifying) materials and products for technical and household purposes;
- creation of materials and products shielding the harmful effects of electric fields and electromagnetic radiation;
- creation of woven electric heating materials and products for technology, medicine and everyday life.
- creation of light and flexible radio-absorbing, radio-scattering and radio-reflecting structures.

Methods have been developed for obtaining and the properties of electrically conductive yarn, fabric and products of various assortments have been studied. It has been established that the introduction of 1-2% of the EPVN conductive fiber into the structure of yarn and fabric makes it possible to obtain a stable antistatic effect.

- a fabric containing in its composition 10 and 30% of the electrically conductive fiber effectively shields, respectively, electric fields and electromagnetic radiation.
- fabrics including 15% electrically conductive fiber can be used to produce electric heating elements for different supply voltages.

Based on the developed domestic electrically conductive fabrics, experimental samples of special professional clothing for protection against electromagnetic radiation were created, and their properties were studied.

Shielding clothing is made of electrically conductive fabric, consisting of cotton and electrically conductive fiber obtained according to Specification 40-02-90.